

Master in Sound and Music Computing
Universitat Pompeu Fabra

Prediction of *Pleasantness* and *Eventfulness* Perceptual Sound Qualities in Urban Soundscapes

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Abstract

The acoustic environment induces emotions in human listeners. To describe such emotions, ISO-12913 defines *pleasantness* and *eventfulness* as orthogonal properties that characterise urban soundscapes. In this work, we study different approaches for automatically estimating these two perceptual sound qualities. We emphasize the comparison of three sets of audio features: a first set from the acoustic and psychoacoustic domain, suggested in ISO-12913; a second set of features from the machine listening domain based on traditional signal processing algorithms; and a third set consisting of audio embeddings generated with a pre-trained audio-language deep-learning model. Each feature set is tested on its own and in combination with ground-truth labels about the sound sources present in the recordings to determine if this additional information improves the prediction accuracy. Our findings indicate that the deep-learning representation yields slightly better performance than the other feature sets when predicting pleasantness, but all of them yield similar performance when predicting eventfulness. Nevertheless, deep-learning embeddings present other advantages, such as faster calculation times and greater robustness against changes in sensor calibration, making them more effective for real-time acoustic monitoring. Furthermore, we observe a clear correlation between the sound sources that are present in the urban soundscape and its induced emotions, specially regarding the sensation of pleasantness. Models like the ones proposed in this paper allow for an assessment of the acoustic environment that goes beyond a characterisation solely based on sound pressure level measurements and could be integrated into current acoustic monitoring solutions to enhance the understanding from the perspective of the induced emotions.

Keywords: Urban soundscapes; acoustic monitoring; emotions; machine-learning; perception

Chapter 1

Introduction

Environmental noise regulations are primarily based on sound pressure level (SPL) measurements. For example, the current European Environmental Noise Directive proposes several SPL-based metrics (like L_d , L_e , L_n and their combination, L_{den}) to determine permitted noise levels [1]. The limit values depend on factors such as the time of the day and the designated noise sensitivity of the evaluated area. However, other perspectives argue that SPL is insufficient to reliably characterise the acoustic environment [2]. Some psychoacoustic parameters such as loudness and sharpness [3], or episodic memory and visual perception [4], also play a role in shaping the perception of an acoustic environment. In this field of research, the concept of *soundscape* is key, defining the perceptual and emotional construct related to a physical phenomenon (the acoustic environment). The study of soundscapes constitutes a big challenge due to the intrinsic nature of emotions: they are triggered, brief and unconscious [5]. Addressing these difficulties, the ISO-12913 [6, 7, 8] determines a framework to enable international consensus on the definition and conceptual foundation of soundscapes. The standard proposes a model with *pleasantness* and *eventfulness* as main orthogonal axes to characterise soundscape emotional responses, based on the evidence that physiological responses to all types of stimuli can be organized along the dimensions of *valence* and *arousal* [9, 10], or *pleasantness* and *eventfulness* when applied to soundscapes [11] (see Figure 1) .

Figure 1: Two-dimensional representation of the affective quality attributed to physical environments generally, left, and to acoustic environments in particular, right.

In this study, we focus on exploring different approaches for automatically estimating the two aforementioned perceptual sound qualities in urban soundscapes. We put emphasis on the comparison of three feature sets for sound representation: the acoustic and psychoacoustic features suggested in ISO-12913, a set of features from the machine listening domain based on traditional signal processing algorithms, and a third set consisting of the audio embeddings generated by a pre-trained language-audio deep-learning model. Each feature set is tested independently and in combination with ground-truth labels about the sound sources present in each recording to determine if this additional information improves the prediction accuracy. Additionally, we examine the models' suitability for real-time acoustic monitoring applications. Our findings indicate that the deep-learning representation yields slightly better performance than the other feature sets when predicting pleasantness, but all of them yield similar results when predicting eventfulness. Nevertheless, deep-learning embeddings present other advantages, such as presumably faster calculation times and greater robustness against changes in sensor calibration, making them more effective for real-time acoustic monitoring. Furthermore, the addition of sound source information improves the prediction accuracy, especially regarding the sensation of pleasantness, indicating a clear correlation between the sound sources that are present in the urban soundscape and its induced emotions. Models like the ones proposed in this paper allow for an assessment of the acoustic environment that goes beyond a characterisation solely based on SPL and could thereby contribute to the development of more accurate acoustic monitoring techniques, enhancing the understanding of the evaluated environment from an emotional perspective.

Structure of the Report

The rest of the report is structured as follows: Chapter 2 presents the state of the art. Chapter 3 describes the methods used, detailing the dataset, the features and the models employed. Chapter 4 explains the evaluation process and Chapter 5 presents the results of the analysis followed by a discussion of the findings and their implications. Finally, Chapter 6 exposes the main conclusion for this research. Additionally, at the end of the report, there are appendices including complementary but important sub-processes related to this work.

Chapter 2

State of the art

In recent years, many studies have focused on the two-dimensional model for soundscape emotion assessment, resulting in the creation of datasets and the experimenting of algorithms on them. Fan et al.[12] present diverse valence/arousal classifications using their own dataset EMO-SOUNDSCAPES [13, 14].

In an analogous way, ATHUS (Athens Urban Soundscape) [15], created by the authors of [16], is a dataset for urban soundscape quality recognition which includes pleasantness and unpleasantness annotations. Similarly, the ARAUS (Affective Responses to Augmented Urban Soundscapes) dataset [17], combines real urban soundscape recordings with different *audio maskers* including *traffic*, *construction*, *water*, *wind*, *bird*, and *silence*, creating a large-scale dataset of *augmented soundscapes* labelled with pleasantness and eventfulness scores obtained from listening tests developed according to the ISO-12913 [18]. Using psychoacoustic features, the authors run preliminary experiments for the estimation of pleasantness.

Existing research on automatic sound classification provides insights which are also useful for addressing soundscape quality assessment. As an example of early work, Salamon et al. [19] present a set of classification experiments using traditional machine-learning algorithms applied to their own developed urban soundscape datasets [20, 21]. Later sound classification works adopted deep neural networks to address more complex classification problems (e.g., [22]). However, the most

Figure 2: Figure from [18]. Mean change in ISO Pleasantness value as a function of each of the 287 maskers used to augment soundscapes in the ARAUS dataset.

recent approaches involve the use of large pre-trained models to extract audio embeddings (i.e. representations) that can be used to address different classification problems and other sound-related tasks such as sound similarity [23]. In particular, Contrastive Language-Audio Pretraining (CLAP) models [24, 25, 26, 27] use contrastive learning to bring audio and text descriptions into a joint multimodal space, and generate sound representations that capture semantically representative information from the audio.

The studies above provide a good framework for research on urban soundscape characterisation. Nevertheless, two important aspects remain unexplored. Firstly, despite existing research showing that the sound sources present in an acoustic environment contribute to its perceived qualities (e.g. natural sounds contribute positively to the pleasantness of an acoustic environment while construction or traffic noise contributes negatively [11, 18], see Figure 2), there is a lack of experiments incorporating such information as an input for automatically characterising soundscapes. Secondly, none of the studies validates the suitability and robustness of the models in real-time contexts, which is essential for the eventual incorporation of the emotional dimension into acoustic monitoring techniques.

Chapter 3

Methods

The core methodology for studying different approaches for predicting the perceptual qualities of pleasantness and eventfulness in urban soundscapes involves data selection, feature extraction, and model training. Our main objective is to evaluate the performance of three different feature sets, and determine which one delivers the best results in terms of accuracy and suitability for real-time applications.

3.1 Dataset

We choose the ARAUS dataset for our experiments because it is the most comprehensive available dataset with pleasantness and eventfulness annotations. ARAUS consists of a set of 25,440 unique and 30s-length augmented audios, created by digitally adding audio maskers (*traffic*, *construction*, *water*, *wind*, *bird*, and *silence*) to real urban soundscape recordings. They are organised in a five-fold cross-validation set and an independent test set. Based on the soundscape study methodology suggested in the ISO-12913, the audio clips are individually labelled with 1-5 ratings on how *pleasant*(p), *annoying*(a), *eventful*(e), *uneventful*(u), *vibrant*(v), *monotonous*(m), *chaotic*(ch) and *calm*(c) they are according to the participants of a listening test. From these ratings, a global value of pleasantness and eventfulness per recording can be calculated using two formulas given in the standard (see Formulas 3.1,3.2). The resulting values range from -1 to 1, where negative values

indicate unpleasantness or uneventfulness, respectively. Additionally, the ARAUS dataset includes, for each augmented soundscape, pre-calculated acoustic and psychoacoustic features recommended by the ISO-12913. These features are calculated with ArtemiS SUITE ¹, which is a proprietary software not easily available to researchers. As part of our work, we provide an open-source Python implementation of such features facilitating the reproducibility of the experiments².

$$P = (p - a) + \cos 45^\circ \cdot (ca - ch) + \cos 45^\circ \cdot (v - m) \quad (3.1)$$

$$E = (e - u) + \cos 45^\circ \cdot (ch - ca) + \cos 45^\circ \cdot (v - m) \quad (3.2)$$

Note: Divide coordinates by $4 + \sqrt{32}$ to obtain a range $[-1, 1]$.

3.2 Features

What follows is a description of the three aforementioned feature sets that we consider for our experiments.

Psychoacoustic features

The standard ISO-12913 suggests a set of acoustic and psychoacoustic features to characterise urban soundscapes: sharpness, loudness, fluctuation strength, roughness, tonality, L_{Aeq} and L_{Ceq} . We compiled existing open source implementations for these features, and wrote custom implementations for the missing ones (see Appendix A for more details about the features' code implementation). For each feature, we use the statistics mean, maximum, and the 5th, 10th, 20th, 30th, 40th, 50th, 60th, 70th, 80th, 90th, and 95th percentiles calculated over time. Additionally, replicating ARAUS, the band powers summed over third-octave bands (5Hz to 20kHz) are included. This results in a total of 117 features. It should be noted that these features should not be computed directly on the WAV signal, but on the peak-Pascals pressure signal that results after applying a gain correction to the raw

¹<https://www.head-acoustics.com/products>

²<https://github.com/amaiasagasti/UrbanPleasantnessEventfulness>

waveform. Thus, the waveform represents the SPL at which the signal was recorded, or, in this case, the level at which it was played in the listening tests. The L_{eq} value, provided for each *augmented soundscape* in the ARAUS dataset, is used to calculate the mentioned calibration factor (designated as *wav gain*). See Appendix B for further explanation.

This feature set is referred to as *ARAUS features*.

Signal processing features

This set includes features typically used in traditional machine listening systems. *Freesound Extractor* algorithm from the Essentia audio analysis library³ generates an extensive set of features from which we use: average loudness; loudness EBU-128; dynamic complexity; spectral flatness, roll-off, flux, skewness, spread, kurtosis and centroid; energy per bands (low, middle-low, middle-high, high); 13th first MFCCs; dissonance; zero-crossing rate; temporal centroid, kurtosis, skewness and spread; log attack-time; inharmonicity; and bpm. For each feature, we compute the statistics mean, variance, and the 20th and 80th percentiles over time, resulting in a total of 139 features. Contrary to the set above, these features are directly linked to the raw audio signal. However, a gain adjustment is performed to ensure that the signal amplitude proportions between different audio clips reflect the volume at which they were played during the listening tests. To achieve this, we apply the corresponding *wav gain* to each audio and then multiply all *augmented soundscapes* by a common normalization factor to prevent clipping (check Appendix B for more details).

This set is referred to as *Freesound features*.

CLAP embeddings

This set of features consists of the 512-length audio embedding generated using LAION-AI’s CLAP model [24]. Since this model is trained using audio-text pairs, the resulting vector is expected to capture semantic information from the audio.

³<https://essentia.upf.edu>

This is unlike the *ARAUS* and *Freesound* feature sets, which only represent acoustic information from the sounds. The same scaling procedure used for the *Freesound* feature set is applied in this case.

This representation is referred to as *CLAP features*.

Note: The above feature sets are tested independently, but also in combination with information about which sound sources are present in the urban soundscape. Ideally, this information should include the predominant sound source. However, no dataset contains realistic urban soundscape sounds with both this source information and the pleasantness/eventfulness annotations. The *ARAUS* dataset provides the maskers (*traffic*, *construction*, *water*, *wind*, *bird*, and *silence*) that were used to generate each augmented soundscape. Even though these sound sources might not always be predominant, it is guaranteed that they are present. Therefore, we use the maskers' information as a proxy for sound source information, and represent it with one-hot vectors.

These six features are referred to as *sources features*.

3.3 Models

The emphasis of this work is not on the models to be trained but on the feature sets. Nevertheless, a number of preliminary experiments were carried out in which the performances of some classic machine learning regression models were compared (like Support Vector Regression, Multi-layer Perceptron Regressor or regression based on K-Nearest-Neighbours). In these experiments, the best results were obtained by an Elastic Net model (as used in [18]), and a Random Forest Regressor. Therefore, these two models are implemented in our experiments using the Scikit-Learn library⁴.

⁴<https://scikit-learn.org>

Chapter 4

Evaluation

To evaluate the predictive performance and robustness of the feature sets and models, we design a multi-faceted evaluation framework which not only includes the use of ARAUS data folds for cross-validation and model testing but it also involves the creation of a new testing set with data not present in the original dataset. Additionally, the analysis of models' robustness against sensor calibration is evaluated by introducing controlled variations in audio signals. Mean Absolute Error (MAE) is used as the main evaluation metric because it allows for a straightforward interpretation that represents the average absolute difference between the predicted and the ground-truth values. The MAE is given by formula 4.1, where n is the number of observations, y_i is the ground-truth value for the i -th observation and \hat{y}_i is the predicted value for the i -th observation.

$$\text{MAE} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |y_i - \hat{y}_i| \quad (4.1)$$

4.1 Data folds

ARAUS includes five folds of augmented soundscapes for cross-validation and one test fold of 48 audios, reported under the labels *Val* and *fold-0* in Table 1, respectively. In addition, we create a complementary testing fold using 25 urban recordings

downloaded from Freesound¹. The selection was carried out manually and consists of 30-second excerpts of real urban environment recordings that include sources such as traffic, construction, rain, wind, voices, and music. Following ISO-12913, a listening test was carried out where 22 participants rated the 25 audios with 1-5 scales on how *pleasant*, *annoying*, *eventful*, *uneventful*, *vibrant*, *monotonous*, *chaotic* and *calm* the soundscapes were perceived. From those ratings, ground-truth pleasantness and eventfulness metrics were calculated following the same standard, using Formulas 3.1 and 3.2. The audios were played at appropriate and varied L_{eq} values, regardless of the audio content. A sonometre was used for calibration. Appendix C gives more details on how the listening test was organised and explains how to obtain the *wav gain* for each of the audios of the new fold.

We refer to this fold as *fold-Fs*.

4.2 Robustness analysis

As has been mentioned, an evaluation of the robustness of the studied models against different input signal calibration conditions is needed for the eventual incorporation of the emotional dimension into acoustic monitoring techniques. For this purpose, five controlled variations of the testing fold *fold-0* are generated by modifying the audio signals with *wav gain* adjustments of -6dB, +6dB, +12dB and +18dB; and a fifth variation with random *wav gain* within a fixed range [0-20dB]. The three feature sets, *ARAUS*, *Freesound* and *CLAP*, are calculated for each of these new five sets of audio signals, and will be inputted into the trained models to check for changes in the prediction accuracy. If the MAE increases, the models will not demonstrate robustness against calibration changes. Conversely, if the MAE remains unaffected, the models will demonstrate the same performance regardless of the calibration.

¹<https://freesound.org>

Chapter 5

Results and Discussion

5.1 Quantitative analysis

Table 1 presents the MAE scores for the different combinations of models and feature sets evaluated. For pleasantness, the CLAP representation outperforms the other two feature sets in both test folds, reaching an MAE of 0.14 in *fold-Fs*. This indicates that, on a scale of $[-1, 1]$, the predictions deviate by an average of 0.14 from the ground-truth values. In terms of MAE variation resulting from the inclusion of the *source features*, the CLAP representation shows the smallest improvement, with just 0.53%, compared to 4.31% for *ARAUS features* and 2.19% for *Freesound features*. Regarding eventfulness, even though we can appreciate similar results for the three feature sets, *ARAUS features* outperform the others when taking into account both test folds. However, the smallest MAE for *fold-Fs*, 0.18 points, is achieved by *CLAP features*. When examining the MAE percentage variation, the inclusion of sound sources information has a smaller impact, with percentages closer to zero than those observed for pleasantness.

Furthermore, all controlled calibration variations generated of *fold-0* result in higher MAE values. Figure 3 illustrates the increase of MAE only for the best-performing model for each feature set. The first noticeable observation is that the impact is greater on eventfulness, where the MAE increase is more pronounced. Also, it can

Feature set	Sound sources info	Model	Train	Val	Test fold-0	Test fold-Fs	Var. %
PLEASANTNESS - MAE							
ARAUS	no	RFR	0.29	0.30	0.24	0.21	4.31
	yes	RFR	0.29	0.29	0.26	0.18	
Freesound	no	EN	0.29	0.30	0.22	0.19	2.19
	yes	EN	0.29	0.29	0.22	0.19	
CLAP	no	RFR	0.10	0.28	0.22	0.14	0.53
	yes	RFR	0.10	0.28	0.22	0.14	
EVENTFULNESS - MAE							
ARAUS	no	EN	0.30	0.30	0.15	0.20	1.57
	yes	EN	0.30	0.30	0.14	0.20	
Freesound	no	RFR	0.13	0.29	0.16	0.22	0.02
	yes	RFR	0.13	0.29	0.16	0.22	
CLAP	no	RFR	0.10	0.29	0.20	0.18	-0.41
	yes	RFR	0.10	0.29	0.20	0.18	

Table 1: MAE results for the best performing models for the cross-validation folds and the two testing folds. The MAE variation percentage is included in the last column, representing the mean percentage variation in MAE when adding the sound sources information to the feature set (a positive percentage indicates an improvement in prediction). Note: *EN* and *RFR* stand for Elastic Net and Random Forest Regressor, respectively.

Figure 3: Increase in MAE value provoked by each *fold-0* variation with respect to the original and unvaried *fold-0* MAE.

be appreciated that the *ARAUS* feature set is more negatively affected in both cases, whereas the *CLAP* feature set appears to be the least affected. Among the variations, the 6dB increase in *wav gain* caused the smaller impact.

In terms of calculation time, *CLAP features* is the fastest set, taking 0.5s to calculate the embeddings for a 30s-long stereo audio file (sampled at 48kHz, run in a MacBook Pro M3). *Freesound features* and *ARAUS features* take 8x and 144x longer, respectively. Note that these numbers should be taken with caution as these three feature sets are implemented in different frameworks and languages, thus a more comprehensive comparison could be done.

5.2 Discussion

The experimental results indicate that, for predicting pleasantness, *CLAP features* outperform the other two sets, achieving an MAE of 0.22 and 0.14 for *fold-0* and *fold-Fs*, respectively. These results occur both when *CLAP features* are used alone and when combined with *sources features*, with only a 0.53% difference in performance between the two scenarios. Since *CLAP* embeddings intrinsically contain semantic information about the audio, additional sound source information is redundant. Conversely, for feature sets that lack this semantic data, including the source information positively impacts the accuracy in the prediction of pleasantness: the performances of *ARAUS* and *Freesound* feature sets improve by 4.31% and 2.19%, respectively. These findings suggest a clear correlation between the sound sources that are present in the urban soundscape and the perceived sensation of pleasantness. In fact, these results coincide with those obtained in the listening test. A quantitative analysis, which can be seen in Figure 4, shows a clear source-class separation on the pleasantness scale depending on the predominant sound source: construction and traffic noises are positioned on the negative side of the axis, while natural sounds are on the positive side. See Appendix D for more details about the analysis of the answers to the listening test.

For predicting eventfulness, all feature sets perform similarly, with *ARAUS features*

Figure 4: Two-dimensional Kernel Density Estimate plot of the pleasantness(P) and eventfulness(E) values reported from the answers to the listening test.

showing slightly better results when considering the MAE mean of both test sets. Besides, the impact of the inclusion of *source features* is negligible, being smaller than 2% for *ARAUS features*, and close to zero for *Freesound* and *CLAP* feature sets. This indicates a weaker correlation between the sound sources present in the soundscape and the sensation of eventfulness, coinciding again with the data extracted from the listening test(Appendix D), where there is more overlap between class groups when seen from the eventfulness axis (see Figure 4).

Determining whether the MAE results achieved for predicting pleasantness and eventfulness are sufficiently accurate is challenging, as there is no existing specific study to serve as a benchmark. However, we can use the results from our listening test as a point of reference. As shown in Table 3 of Appendix D, the mean standard deviations for the pleasantness and eventfulness values obtained from the answers to the listening test are 0.27 and 0.31, respectively. Our algorithm achieved MAE values of 0.14 and 0.18 on the same set of audios. Given the subjective, personal and

complex nature of emotions, the achieved MAE values seem reasonable, suggesting that the developed predictive algorithms perform acceptably well.

In terms of robustness against changes in sensor calibration, none of the trained models demonstrate strong capabilities, as MAE increases notably in every *fold-0* variation case. Nevertheless, predictions of eventfulness are more negatively affected, potentially indicating a correlation between SPL, or loudness, and the perception of eventfulness. In other words, regardless of the audio content, changes in volume seem to significantly alter the perception of eventfulness: what was initially perceived as eventful can become uneventful, and vice versa. Moreover, models trained with *CLAP features* seem to be slightly less impacted by the calibration changes. In addition to this, their rapid generation time suggests that *CLAP features* are adequate for real-time contexts.

5.3 Further work – *Soundlights*

Models like the ones proposed in this paper allow for an assessment of the acoustic environment that goes beyond a characterisation solely based on sound pressure level measurements and could be integrated into existing acoustic monitoring solutions to enhance the understanding of the environment from the perspective of the induced emotions.

In fact, this Master Thesis research was carried out in the context of *Soundlights*. This project aims to implement the developed models in a network of outdoor sensors across the city of Barcelona. The primary objective is to collect real-time audio data of the acoustic environment, analyze it to predict perceptual information, and map and display the results as warning messages on visual interfaces like LED screens. By providing real-time feedback, this system aims to influence and shape the behavior of citizens (like traffic-lights), thus enhancing the quality of the urban soundscape both immediately and in the long term.

In addition to the pleasantness and eventfulness predictive models developed in this work, we are also focused on developing and implementing sound source identifica-

tion models. This will enable the sensor to not only predict how pleasant or eventful the urban soundscape is but also identify the source of the noise or activity. A video simulation of the first versions of the working algorithm is available¹.

Ultimately, besides its technological innovative approach, *Soundlights* aims to create a more comfortable and pleasant social environment in the busy city. The collected data provides valuable quantitative and qualitative information that can help raise awareness about issues related to excessive noise in Barcelona and potentially prompt authorities to implement noise-reducing solutions, thereby improving the environmental perception and the overall well-being of its inhabitants.

See the collaborators and funders of *Soundlights* in Acknowledgement section.

¹<https://youtu.be/fsis40ViLwQ>

Chapter 6

Conclusion

This research shows that CLAP embeddings generated by LAION-AI’s CLAP model demonstrate high performance as input to models for predicting *pleasantness* and *eventfulness* perceptual sound qualities. Even though the sound representation does not present strong robustness to variations in sensor calibration, it can be computed rapidly, making it suitable for real-time applications. Moreover, our study indicates a clear correlation between the sound sources present in an urban soundscape and its sensation of pleasantness. Future research directions could include evaluating the developed models in the context of a real-world acoustic sensor network and incorporating sound classification and source separation technologies to improve the models’ accuracy and capabilities for meaningful soundscape characterisation and monitoring.

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Appendices

Appendix A

Acoustic and Psychoacoustic features code implementation

ARAUS dataset provides, for all *augmented soundscapes*, the summary statistics for a set of acoustic and psychoacoustic indicators as recommended by ISO-12913. As part of this project, we offer an open-source code implementation of these features. For a deeper understanding of how this feature set is generated, it is advisable to review the actual code¹. However, here is a brief explanation of what these features represent and how they are calculated.

Sharpness: It represents the sensation of timbre with emphasis on high frequency content. The calculation of this parameter is done according to DIN-45692 [28].

Loudness: It describes the relative sensation of sound strength perceived by a listener with otologically normal hearing. It shows a high correspondence with the sensation of volume. The calculation of this parameter is done according to ISO-532/1 [29].

Fluctuation Strength: It describes the perceptual phenomenon of loudness changing slowly up and down at the low modulation frequency of 4Hz. There

¹<https://github.com/amaiasagasti/UrbanPleasantnessEventfulness>

is not an standardized computation method for this parameter but there are computational models available in Fastl and Zwicker's work [30].

Roughness: It describes the perceptual phenomenon of loudness changing quickly up and down at the high modulation frequency of 70Hz. There is not an standardized computation method for this parameter but there are computational models available in Fastl and Zwicker's work [30].

Tonality: It represents another sensation of timbre which indicates whether a sound consists mainly of tonal components or broadband sound. There are standards to compute tonality, but they do not model the psychoacoustic impression of tonality. However, ECMA-74 and ECMA-418/2 do propose approaches to compute this psychoacoustic parameter [31, 32].

L_{Aeq} : It represents the exponentially averaged sound pressure level computed with fast averaging (125 milliseconds), adjusted to reflect the sensitivity of human hearing to different frequencies by applying frequency weighting (*A-weighting*). It is usually used for low volume sounds.

L_{Ceq} : It represents the exponentially averaged sound pressure level computed with fast averaging (125 milliseconds), being more responsive to low-frequency sounds compared to L_{Aeq} by applying frequency weighting (*C-weighting*). It is usually used for high volume sounds.

Note: Due to time constraints, the complexity involved in generating certain parameters, and because this was not the primary focus of this Master Thesis, some parameters have not been fully implemented. Specifically, as no pre-existing code implementations were found for Fluctuation Strength and Roughness, a simplified approximation was used instead (see the code for more details on the calculations). Tonality was not implemented.

Figure 5: Psychoacoustic features comparison between original ARAUS dataset and ARAUS-extended dataset.

Figure 5 shows the comparison between some of the original ARAUS feature values and those calculated, for the 48 audios of *Fold-0*. It can be appreciated that they are not exact. This could be due to the *wav gain* calculation process prior to the features calculation, or to small variations in the features calculation process itself.

Nevertheless, as a way of validating this feature implementation code so that we could proceed with the rest of the project, the Elastic Net model used by the ARAUS authors to predict pleasantness was reused. The same conditions were maintained, but the newly calculated features were introduced instead. In fact, this resulted in slightly better performance of the predictive model than that achieved with ARAUS original feature set. This happened because fluctuation strength, roughness and tonality parameters did not have significant feature importance in the Elastic Net model. Therefore, we continued with the research.

Appendix B

Signal gain adjustments

ARAUS dataset provides the code to generate the 25,440 unique augmented urban soundscapes in WAV format together with a CSV file, *responses.csv*, with metadata about those audios. This meta-information includes the reference to the original urban soundscape recording on which the augmentation was made, the masker used, the ratings given in the listening tests, the L_{eq} for each urban soundscape... These L_{eq} values represent the SPL at which the audio files were played in the listening tests, or in other words, their volume. L_{eq} results from the exponentially averaged sound pressure level (in decibels) over time of the sound pressure signal samples of the augmented soundscape (with no weighting filter applied), computed with fast averaging (time constant of 125 milliseconds). See Formula B.1.

$$L_{eq} = 10 \log_{10} \left(\frac{1}{T} \int_0^T p_{fast}(t)^2 dt \right) \quad (\text{B.1})$$

L_{eq} can be used to calculate the factor that converts the WAV digital signal (ranged from -1 to 1) into the peak-Pascals pressure signal. Figure 6 shows the process to do this calculation: Firstly, Formula B.1 is directly applied to the WAV signal of the augmented urban soundscape. The obtained *raw* L_{eq} is subtracted from the given L_{eq} . Finally, the difference between these two SPL levels transformed to linear results in the searched factor or *wav gain*.

Figure 6: Calculation schema of *wav gain*, factor that converts the digital signal into the peak-Pascals pressure signal.

Figure 7: Transformation of the original WAV signal.

The set of acoustic and psychoacoustic features are calculated on the peak-Pascals pressure signal that results after applying *wav gain* to the digital signal, whereas the other two feature sets, *Freesound features* and *CLAP features* are calculated on the digital signal. Nevertheless, the WAV audio signal requires some processing prior to the calculation of both feature sets.

The reasoning for this processing lies on the signal amplitude proportion between different WAV audio files. Instead of the raw amplitude proportions, the amplitude relation between the different digital signals should correspond to the volumes at which they were played during the listening tests. To achieve this, each augmented soundscape WAV is multiplied by its *wav gain* factor, resulting in the peak-Pascals signal. Then, all peak-Pascals signals are normalised by a common factor to convert them back to digital signals within the range $[-1,1]$ (refer to the process outlined in Figure 7). The normalisation factor is 6.44 as an analysis showed that it prevents clipping in 95% of the WAV files. See aclaratory note below for a more detailed explanation.

Example case: Consider two augmented soundscapes from the ARAUS dataset. The digital signal of *Augmented Soundscape 1* has a smaller amplitude than that of *Augmented Soundscape 2*. However, the provided L_{eq} values for each soundscape indicate that *Augmented Soundscape 1* was played at a higher volume during the listening test than *Augmented Soundscape 2*. Consequently, the *wav gain* for *Augmented Soundscape 1* is greater than that for *Augmented Soundscape 2*. When these factors are applied to their respective digital signals, the resulting physical peak-Pascals signal for *Augmented Soundscape 1* has a higher amplitude than that of *Augmented Soundscape 2*. This demonstrates that the amplitude proportion of the original digital signals (WAV files) differs from the amplitude relation of the physical signals reproduced during the listening test. By applying a common normalization gain to all augmented soundscapes, *norm gain*, the physical signals are converted back into digital format with the appropriate amplitude proportions. As a result, all three feature sets can be computed on signals that maintain the same amplitude proportions as they had during the listening test.

Appendix C

Listening test preparation

The ISO-12913/2 specifies the requirements and supporting information on data collection and reporting for soundscape studies. It proposes diverse data collection tools and methods, some of which can be applied *in situ* (soundwalks) and some others are carried out in situations where sound is reproduced by headphones or loudspeakers. For the latter case, the standard defines an appropriate test design. Based on the proposed guidelines for data collection via loudspeakers, a listening test was conducted. The following sections explain the process of preparation in more detail.

Loudspeaker Arrangement

For the playback of binaural measurements, a loudspeaker arrangement based on four loudspeakers allows a binaural reproduction with comparable results to using headphones. In this listening test, the loudspeakers were positioned in a square formation around a central point equidistantly at 3.5 meters. The two left-hand loudspeakers received the left channel whereas the right-hand ones received the right channel of the stereo audio files. This loudspeaker arrangement allows 4 participants taking the test at the same time (see arrangement schema in Figure 8 and real scenario in Figure 9).

The speakers' orientation was facing the middle division line that separates the L-R

Figure 8: Loud-speaker layout in listening test. Red crosses represent the participants.

Figure 9: Real loud-speaker layout in listening test.

sides, but not directly to the center point as it risked causing phase cancellation (phenomenon where sound waves from multiple sources interfere with each other). To prevent this issue and ensure consistent sound quality, we carefully adjusted the speaker positions to avoid any destructive interference.

Regarding loudspeakers calibration, a pink noise audio file was used for calibration together with a sonometer. Once this recording was adjusted to the correct level, the entire set of urban soundscape recordings presented in the listening test was calibrated accordingly to ensure that the desired L_{eq} values were achieved.

Audio Guideline Setup

A set of 25 urban soundscape recordings were manually chosen and downloaded from the Freesound library (see audio references below). The selected sound files contained a wide variety of typical urban sound sources like traffic, construction, birds, rain, wind, music and people chattering.

The listening test was presented to the participants as a guided audio where a guiding voice gave instructions and reproduced the 25 audio recordings (30 second excerpts from each of the audio files) one after the other, with 30 seconds of silence between each soundscape. This gap time allowed participants to answer and attempted to avoid auditory habituation (prolonged exposure to certain sounds can cause them to become less noticeable and less annoying over time).

Three different versions of the audio guideline were created, with each version presenting the soundscapes in a unique random order. This approach helps ensure that the responses are more reliable by minimizing any biases that could arise from the order in which the recordings are reproduced, (an example audio guideline can be found in the footnote link¹).

List of Freesound Sounds References				
242118	451734	391460	93033	202427
483074	342429	667056	677186	23063
242118	656340	106205	205838	173154
170587	413913	402369	453430	155281
639229	521982	380651	257421	564637

Lastly, prior to the listening test, it was necessary to determine the L_{eq} levels at which each soundscape recording would be played. To achieve this, we examined the distribution of the L_{eq} values used in ARAUS dataset and aimed to replicate it as closely as possible (see Figure 10). Additionally, we ensured that audio files with similar sound source content were assigned a diverse range of L_{eq} levels for variety.

¹<https://youtu.be/A3Ufg1e0dPo>

Figure 10: Normalized 25 bins histogram of L_{eq} values from ARAUS original dataset (left) and *Fold-Fs*(right).

Answers Sheet

Annex C of the standard ISO-12913/2 outlines various data collection methods for assessing how people perceive an acoustic environment. Following *Method A - Questionnaire*, an answer sheet was created for participants to use while and after listening to the 25 urban soundscapes.

At the beginning of the answer sheet, participants were asked to provide some personal information, including their name or pseudonym, age, any hearing disabilities, and whether their profession is related to music. Participants were informed in advance about how their data would be used, and they were assured that answering all the questions was optional.

Then, for each recording, participants were asked three questions (see Figure 11). The first question aimed to characterize the presented acoustic environment by identifying which sound sources could be heard and their dominance. The second part addressed the perceived affective quality of the soundscapes, with participants rating eight different affective attributes on a scale from *Strongly agree* to *Strongly disagree*. Finally, participants were asked to provide an overall description of the sound environment.

URBAN SOUNDSCAPES SURVEY

NAME/PSEUDONIM _____ AGE _____ ANY HEARING DISABILITY? _____

GENDER: Male Female Non-binary Prefer Not to Answer OCCUPATION RELATED TO SOUND Yes No

QUESTIONS

To what extent do you presently hear the following four types of sources?

Traffic noise (cars, buses, trains, planes...)

Other noise (sirens, construction works, loading of loads...)

Sounds from human beings (conversational, laughter, children, music, footsteps...)

Natural sounds (singing birds, water, wind in vegetation...)

For each of the 8 scales below, to what extent do you agree or disagree that the present surrounding environment is...

PLEASANT VIBRANT CALM EVENTFUL
CHAOTIC UNEVENTFUL ANNOYING MONOTONOUS

Overall, how would you describe the presented sound environment?

Very bad Bad Neutral Good Very good

SOUNDSCAPE 1

Not at all A little Moderately A lot Dominates

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Moderately	Agree	Strongly Agree
PLEASANT					
CHAOTIC					
VIBRANT					
UNEVENTFUL					
CALM					
ANNOYING					
EVENTFUL					
MONOTONOUS					

OVERALL

Very good

Good

Neutral

Bad

Very bad

SOUNDSCAPE 2

Not at all A little Moderately A lot Dominates

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Moderately	Agree	Strongly Agree
PLEASANT					
CHAOTIC					
VIBRANT					
UNEVENTFUL					
CALM					
ANNOYING					
EVENTFUL					
MONOTONOUS					

OVERALL

Very good

Good

Neutral

Bad

Very bad

SOUNDSCAPE 3

Not at all A little Moderately A lot Dominates

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Moderately	Agree	Strongly Agree
PLEASANT					
CHAOTIC					
VIBRANT					
UNEVENTFUL					
CALM					
ANNOYING					
EVENTFUL					
MONOTONOUS					

OVERALL

Very good

Good

Neutral

Bad

Very bad

SOUNDSCAPE 4

Not at all A little Moderately A lot Dominates

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Moderately	Agree	Strongly Agree
PLEASANT					
CHAOTIC					
VIBRANT					
UNEVENTFUL					
CALM					
ANNOYING					
EVENTFUL					
MONOTONOUS					

OVERALL

Very good

Good

Neutral

Bad

Very bad

SOUNDSCAPE 5

Not at all A little Moderately A lot Dominates

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Moderately	Agree	Strongly Agree
PLEASANT					
CHAOTIC					
VIBRANT					
UNEVENTFUL					
CALM					
ANNOYING					
EVENTFUL					
MONOTONOUS					

OVERALL

Very good

Good

Neutral

Bad

Very bad

SOUNDSCAPE 6

Not at all A little Moderately A lot Dominates

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Moderately	Agree	Strongly Agree
PLEASANT					
CHAOTIC					
VIBRANT					
UNEVENTFUL					
CALM					
ANNOYING					
EVENTFUL					
MONOTONOUS					

OVERALL

Very good

Good

Neutral

Bad

Very bad

Figure 11: Single page extracted from the answer sheet given to participants of the listening test.

Appendix D

Listening test results

A total of 22 participants with no hearing disabilities took part in the listening test, with an equal distribution of male and female participants. Among them, 77% were under 30 years old, and a total of 82% worked in sound-related professions. They took the test in groups of 2-4 people simultaneously. Each of the three versions of the audio guideline (with different order variations of the presented audios) was taken by 7, 7, and 8 participants, respectively.

As an initial step in the analysis, we examined whether auditory habituation occurred. Figure 12 displays the count of "moderate" or "neutral" responses (middle answers to the second and third questions for each recording) given at each position in the soundscapes sequence of the audio guideline. An indication of habituation would be an increase in the number of these answers as the listening test progressed. However, the trend lines remain relatively constant, suggesting no habituation effect.

Sound Source identification	Not at all 1	A little 2	Moderately 3	A lot 4	Dominates 5
Affective Quality	Strongly disagree 5	Disagree 4	Moderately 3	Agree 2	Strongly Agree 1
Overall Assessment	Very good 5	Good 4	Neutral 3	Bad 2	Very bad 1

Table 2: Assigned value scales to rating scales of listening test according to ISO-12913/3.

Figure 12: Count of intermediate answers as urban soundscapes are progressively presented in the listening test.

The standard ISO-12913/3 provides guidelines on how to analyse the collected quantitative responses. It proposes scale values to rating scales, shown in Table 2.

We first analyse and plot the histogram of the mean affective quality ratings given by the participants in relation to the dominant sound sources present in the urban soundscapes. In Figure 13, it can be appreciated that when both construction and traffic sound sources are predominant, the affective qualities with the most number of answers are *chaotic*, *annoying* and *eventful*. Regarding human sounds dominant recordings, *chaotic*, *vibrant* and *eventful* are agreed to be the most suitable affective qualities. Finally, when nature sounds are dominant, *pleasantness* quality has the highest mean rating followed by *calm* and *monotonous*.

Proceeding with the analysis, formulas 3.1 and 3.2 are used to transform the affective quality ratings to pleasantness and eventfulness values. Figure 14 constitutes the one-dimensional versions of Figure 4. They represent the KDE distribution of pleasantness and eventfulness ratings related to the dominant sound sources in the audio recordings (nature, human, traffic, and construction).

The KDE graph of pleasantness values, reveals minimal overlapping between the four distribution graph lines indicating that the sound sources present in an urban soundscape have significant influence on the perceived pleasantness. Participants answers demonstrate the strong impact the type of sounds have on how pleasant an

Figure 13: Participants’ mean ratings of eight affective attributes related to the dominant sound sources.

environment is perceived to be.

Regarding the KDE graph for eventfulness, it shows more overlapping between the distribution lines for the different sound classes. This indicates that participants did not find a strong relationship between the sound sources present in the recordings and the perceived sensation of eventfulness. The overlapping distributions suggest a weaker correlation between specific sound sources and the perception of eventfulness.

This analysis reveals a consensus, especially regarding pleasantness, among participants on how urban sound sources influence the perception of a soundscape. This leads to the belief that including the sound sources as inputs or using a sound representation with semantic information in an AI-model could improve its predictive accuracy.

It can also be interesting to evaluate the level of agreement among participants for each recording presented in the listening test. This analysis could offer a better understanding of the expected accuracy of the predictive models. In Table 3, the standard deviation can be interpreted as the level of agreement between participants. It is clear that the perception of an urban soundscape is quite subjective.

Figure 14: One-dimensional Kernel Density Estimate plot of the pleasantness(left) and eventfulness(right) values reported from the answers to the listening test. Dashed lines represent mean values.

Audio File	Pleasantness	Eventfulness
freesound_564637	0.57 ± 0.22	-0.06 ± 0.25
freesound_23063	-0.40 ± 0.21	0.09 ± 0.27
freesound_93033	-0.10 ± 0.37	-0.15 ± 0.35
freesound_106205	0.25 ± 0.30	-0.34 ± 0.34
freesound_155281	0.38 ± 0.26	0.18 ± 0.32
freesound_170587	-0.13 ± 0.26	0.38 ± 0.39
freesound_173154	-0.37 ± 0.15	0.19 ± 0.32
freesound_202427	-0.25 ± 0.17	0.00 ± 0.33
freesound_205838	0.20 ± 0.25	-0.15 ± 0.23
freesound_242188	0.43 ± 0.21	0.31 ± 0.30
freesound_639229	0.18 ± 0.16	0.13 ± 0.29
freesound_257421	-0.53 ± 0.15	0.49 ± 0.22
freesound_342429	0.10 ± 0.22	0.56 ± 0.27
freesound_380651	0.27 ± 0.30	-0.38 ± 0.28
freesound_391460	-0.16 ± 0.23	0.30 ± 0.22
freesound_402369	-0.04 ± 0.33	0.06 ± 0.30
freesound_413913	-0.13 ± 0.18	0.48 ± 0.21
freesound_451734	-0.15 ± 0.25	0.49 ± 0.30
freesound_453430	-0.35 ± 0.21	0.13 ± 0.29
freesound_483074	0.18 ± 0.24	0.54 ± 0.22
freesound_521982	-0.22 ± 0.32	0.03 ± 0.26
freesound_656340	-0.01 ± 0.24	0.34 ± 0.31
freesound_667056	-0.11 ± 0.26	0.15 ± 0.28
freesound_677186	-0.54 ± 0.23	0.33 ± 0.28
freesound_686384	-0.02 ± 0.29	0.52 ± 0.27
Mean Standard Deviation	0.27	0.31

Table 3: Mean and Standard Deviation of Pleasantness and Eventfulness values obtained from the answers to the listening test for each audio file.